

Synthesis of N-Ethyl-N'-2-Benzothiazolyl Guanidines and their use as Possible Algacides

G. C. Singh

Seven N-ethyl-N'-2-(substituted-benzothiazolyl)-thiocarbamides have been synthesised by condensation of ethylisothiocyanate and different 2-aminobenzothiazoles. The thiocarbamides have been converted into guanidines and subsequently into their hydrochlorides for testing their algacidal activity.

Rose and Swain¹ prepared and studied the biological activities of a series of bis-diguanides. Ram² synthesised some diaryl guanidines in which one aryl group was substituted benzothiazole and another was phenyl or substituted phenyl group and studied their antibacterial property. In view of the fact that guanidines have been found to possess high degree of antibacterial activity, several N-ethyl-N'-2-(substituted-benzothiazolyl)-guanidines have been synthesised and their algacidal properties have been tested.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Ethyl-N'-2-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide: Ethylisothiocyanate (3 ml) and 2-aminobenzothiazole (5 g) were refluxed for 4 hours. The excess of ethylisothiocyanate and 2-aminobenzothiazole were removed by washing several times with ether and dil. HCl. The thiocarbamidethus obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 198°, yield 90% (Found: N, 17.60; S, 26.88; C₁₀H₁₁N₃S₂ requires N, 17.72; S, 27%).

Similarly, various substituted N-ethyl-N'-2-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides were prepared. Their melting points and analytical data are listed in table I.

TABLE I

N-Ethyl-N'-2-(substituted-benzothiazolyl)-thiocarbamides

S. N.	Nature of X	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%		Sulphur %	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	4-Methyl	226.5	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	16.79	16.73	25.41	25.50
2.	5-Methyl	220	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	16.60	16.73	25.43	25.50
3.	6-Methyl	196	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	16.70	16.73	25.29	25.50
4.	6-Chloro	212	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	15.29	15.47	23.40	23.57
5.	6-Methoxy	215	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	15.59	15.73	23.69	23.97
6.	6-Ethoxy	202	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS ₂	14.80	14.95	25.59	22.78

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4422.

2. Ram, Ph. D. thesis, Banaras Hindu University, 1963.

N-Ethyl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolyl guanidine: *N*-Ethyl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide quantitatively formed *N*-ethyl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolyl guanidines when heated with yellow lead oxide and ethanolic ammonia in a sealed tube. The product was crystallised from 50% ethanol, m.p. 164.5° (Found: N, 25.30; S, 14.40; C₁₀H₁₂N₄S requires N, 25.46; S, 14.53%). Hydrochloride, m.p. 215°.

Similarly, various substituted-*N*-ethyl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolyl guanidines and their hydrochlorides were prepared. Their melting points and analytical data are recorded in table II.

TABLE II

N-Ethyl-*N'*-2-(substituted-benzothiazolyl)-guanidines

S.N.	Nature of X	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen %		Sulphur %		Guanidine hydro- chloride, m.p.°C
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	
1.	4-Methyl	180	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	23.80	23.93	13.49	13.68	278-79
2.	5-Methyl	163	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	23.70	23.93	13.51	13.68	248-49
3.	6-Methyl	150	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	23.74	23.93	13.80	13.68	249
4.	6-Chloro	170	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ SCl	21.99	22.01	12.37	12.57	210-11
5.	6-Methoxy	182	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O	22.20	22.41	12.48	12.80	262
6.	6-Ethoxy	161	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	21.18	21.21	12.00	12.12	181

ALGAECIDAL ACTIVITY SCREENING

Out of all the guanidine hydrochlorides screened against unicellular alga *Anacystis nidulans*, hydrochloride of *N*-ethyl-*N'*-2(6-chloro-benzothiazolyl)-guanidine was found to be most active. The details will be published elsewhere.

Thanks are due to Dr. P. N. Bhargava, Reader in Organic Chemistry for his keen interest and valuable guidance, authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing necessary facilities and to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.